

Andrej Poleev · Charitéplatz 1 · 10117 Berlin

Governor Gavin Newsom
1303 10th Street, Suite 1173
Sacramento, CA 95814
USA

29.10.2020

Due to its involvement in a prohibited organization {1}, continuation of lawbreaking by its staff, and disregard of my decision of 2.04.2020 {2}, I prohibit Google LLC and confirm seizure of its assets and property aimed to prevent committing tortious acts.

Both local and federal administrations are obliged to implement said legal measures by applying appropriate laws, i.a. antitrust laws. {3}

In case of refusal to fulfill their duties, the staff of these administrations will be subjected to sanctions against them for complicity in lawbreaking. {4}

Dr. Andrej Poleev

References.

1. World Association of News Publishers: List of members.

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4. Πνεῦμα κατανύξεως.

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καθάπερ γέγραπται "Ἐδωκεν αὐτοῖς ὁ Θεὸς πνεῦμα κατανύξεως, ὀφθαλμοὺς τοῦ μὴ βλέπειν καὶ ὦτα τοῦ μὴ ἀκούειν, ἕως τῆς σήμερον ἡμέρας. As it is written, "God gave them a spirit of stupor, eyes that would not see and ears that would not hear, to this very day." – [Romans 11:8](#)

Πνεῦμα κατανύξεως – a spirit of stupor, which renders their souls torpid, i. e. so insensible that they are not affected at all by the offer made them of salvation through the Messiah. The term is also related to German „geistige Umnachtung“ and „Blödsinn“ („dementia“) in psychoanalytic sense as described by Eugene Bleuler in his monograph on schizophrenia.

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νύξ, νυκτός the night, night-time, μέσης νυκτός at midnight. Metaphorically, the time when work ceases, i. e. the time of death, John 9:4; the time for deeds of sin and shame, the time of moral stupidity and darkness, Romans 13:12; the time when the weary and also the drunken give themselves up to slumber, put for torpor and sluggishness, 1 Thessalonians 5:5.

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Market share [\[edit\]](#)

As of September 2020,^[41] **Google** is the world's most used search engine, with a market share of 92.96 percent, and the world's most used search engines are:

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Xavier Becerra
Office of the Attorney General
1300 "I" Street
Sacramento, CA 95814-2919
USA

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Jim Cooper
State Capitol
Room 6025
Sacramento, CA 95814
USA

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Mayor Margaret Abe-Koga
City Hall
500 Castro Street, 3rd Floor
Mountain View, CA 94041-2010
USA

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